

Clarify Interaction Between Emotion and Cognition

Focus on Interface User

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Abstract

It is considered that emotion satisfies us and attracts us to use and love products, while cognition makes use to understand knowledgeably how to use products. In this study, we aimed studying the interaction between emotion and cognition focus on product interface user. Centered with a suggested model of interaction between cognition and emotion, we considered principally that cognitive processing was mainly performed when user operated on product. We devoted ways to investigate, the first, how emotion worked during and after operation; the second, whether emotion influenced cognition during operation, or the cognition influenced emotion. Two experimental case studies were planned according to the targets. In each case, users' emotions were evaluated in two ways including EEG and subjective evaluation, while cognitions were observed through operation data.

In first case study, drivers' comfortable feelings on curvilinear motion were observed by frontal lobe Alpha waves and subjective evaluation.

In second case study, a program was developed to realize the mental-rotation in virtual environment in which the interface background color could be changed. We observed that if user's emotions could be excited by color information and its interactions with cognitive operation.

The study indicates that emotion would be performed independently responding to information dynamically in the state that cognitive processing is mainly performed while using product. Sometimes emotional reactions show connections with cognition, even if it did not be reflected on operational behaviors or physiological indicators, it would be memorized implicitly, and aroused consciously by subjective evaluation after operation.

Conference theme: Teaching across cultures design

Key words: product interface, emotion, cognition.

1 Introduction

Both cognition and emotion are the information processing system of human beings. In recently the interface studies emphasis on how to improve user emotional experience in interface design. It is considered that emotion satisfies us and attracts us to use and love products, while cognition makes use to understand knowledgeably how to use products. Either emotion or cognition is processed by our mind when we are facing information, but it is not clear yet that how the emotion and cognition works and how interact between them.

The psychological post studies indicate that emotions play an essential role in decision making, mood dependent memory, and rational thinking [1,2]. Also in the research field of User Interface, many studies concentrated on confirming the relationships between cognition and emotion when user uses computer or product. According to the study of Masaaki Kurosu and Kaori Kashimura [3], apparent usability is strongly affected by the aesthetic aspects rather than the inherent usability on interface of cash dispenser. The research of Hiltz,S.R and Johnson,K[4] showed that if computer were perceived initially as difficulty to user, users were more likely to express dissatisfaction with the interface of the system after four months use. Jared M, Spool *el* [5] showed the user's preference on web site related to task operation, because the list order of user's abhorrence on web site was similarly to the order of task accomplishment through the web set. According to these post studies, it is clear that user's positive affect from aesthetic of product could effect on user's rational understanding about interface; and more, the relationships were confirmed between emotional evaluation and cognitional activity on interface. Even though so much post researches confirmed the relationship between emotion and cognition, and in the psychology effect of emotion on cognition was commonly studied through experiment of words recital in laboratory. Literature research shows that seldom study described the interplay between emotion and cognition especially in the research field of interface user.

About user's emotion on product interface, Norman attributed emotion in three different levels of visceral, behavioral and reflective [5]. He suggested that product design should design the user's emotional experience from three levels as well as design rational usability of product interface. Here we prefer to point that it is important to understand how emotion and cognition interact before the emotional experiences are practically induced to product interface design. The research did not stop in the post researches that only proves the relations between emotion and cognition on UI, we discussed the interaction between emotion and cognition especially in the situation when user using product.

2 Suggestion on Model of Interaction Between cognition and Emotion

Literature researches show that both cognition and emotion are parallel and interactive processing system for adaptable reactions to information [6]. Especially facing the product using, we would like to suggest the Interactive Model Between Cognition and Emotion showing as figure 1.

Figure 1. Interaction Model Between cognition and Emotion

In the model, Emotion is intuitive information processing system that produces intuitive appreciations from perceiving information, such as pleasures, comfortableness, as well as feeling and impression reflected upon the past experience, such as like or disgust etc.

Cognition is active information processing to recognize the information, perform an appropriate act by a series of thinking such as judgment, decision, memory, the reasoning, discovery and problem solving.

The process of product operation can be seen as the state that cognition processing is mainly performed consciously when user is using product motivated by purposes, while emotion works unconsciously in this state.

The user's reactions including behaviors, physiological responses and subjective evaluations can be considered as the results of interaction between cognition and emotion. Our studies were centered with the Model to measure the user's reactions from these three aspects, and the interactions between emotion and cognition were discussed by analyze three kinds of reactions.

3 Objective of the research

We aimed to investigate the interlays between emotion and cognition from two aspects, the one was how emotion worked in the states that cognitive processing was mainly performed; the second, whether emotion influenced cognition during operation, or the cognition influenced

emotion. The two experimental case studies were planned according to these basic thoughts. It was very important to record the user's operational behaviors and emotional states while operating product or program. We engaged ways to observe cognition by indicators of operation, and to observe emotional states through physiological reactions and subjective evaluations (seen in 4).

In the first case study, the experiments of drive in curvilinear motion were designed. We aimed to investigate how the emotions worked through observing the emotion states reflected by drivers' physiological response during driving and subjective evaluation after driving.

In the second experimental study, a program was developed to realize the 'mental-rotation' in PC virtual environment in which the interface background color could be chosen by user's favor. We aimed to investigate whether user's emotional states could be excited by background color information, and whether it effected on cognitional activities while users were operating the program.

In each case study, we discussed interplays between cognition and emotion through analyzing the correlations between the indicators of emotional states and operating behaviors.

4 how to evaluate emotion

Emotion evaluation is an important issue in the interface evaluation. It is suggested that emotion can be examined in terms of two components: cognitive and physical [7]. Cognitive component focus on understanding the situation that give rise to emotions, and physical component emphasizes the physiological response that co-occurs with emotion. Same as the theory, we tried ways to evaluate emotion from the two components: subjective evaluation and physiological evaluation.

4.1 Subjective evaluation

Subjective evaluation is to let user self-express on emotion by subjective verbal describe or SD (Semantic Differential) Method. It is usually be used after user had finished operation.

4.2 Physiological evaluation

Many experiences of human bodily changes can be the indicators of emotion, poses of body, hand perspiring, hearts rate increasing, sweaty palms, and brain waves. Because of the complexity of emotions in mechanism and expressions, researches are presently no sufficient to discriminate and evaluate emotions from full expressions, such as anger, happiness, sadness, surprise, disgust or fear. In our research, despite so much emotional expressions, we only chose one kind of emotional states of comfortableness as the evaluating content.

From the dictionary, comfort is defined as 'a feeling physically relaxed and satisfied'. In recently years, many researches devoted to study how the products or environments could arouse user's comfortableness, for example, comfortableness of clothes, automobiles and interiors. It is also important that what physiological indices are useful to measure comfortable

states. Recently, it had shown that comfortableness could be gotten by using "1/f fluctuation" of air currently changes periodically in automobile industry field [8]. Musha [9] had succeeded to objectively measure the relationship between comfortableness and fluctuation, and clarified the frequency fluctuation of the alpha wave of the brain influences human's feelings. The evaluation of the fluctuation of alpha wave of the brain is thought to be effective for evaluating comfortableness. Moreover, Yoshida [10] proposed "basic affection vector model" in which comfortableness evaluation suggested to be expressed by two dimensions known as valence (positive-negative) and arousal (excited-calm), and 1/f-linked frequency fluctuation in left/ right Frontal Alpha Waves accompanying with comfortable feelings can be measured objectively as indicators of the two dimensions. The left frontal frequency fluctuations of alpha express human's valence (positive-negative), while the right frontal express arousal (excited-calm). When both left and right absolute value of slope coefficients of frontal frequency fluctuations of alpha near the rhythm degree 1 of "1/f fluctuation", it means human is in the state of "calm comfort". Moreover, the comfortableness degree is calculated by left and right frontal frequency fluctuations of alpha, as a degree of comfort to evaluate comfortableness quantitatively. Corresponding to the model, Yoshida further developed a non-invasive measuring apparatus [HSK-centered rhythm monitor slim] to evaluate person's comfortableness chronologically in real time series. In our researches, we employed the apparatus to measure user's comfortableness as physiological expression of emotional states.

Study

Case Study 1 Evaluating Drivers' Comfortableness in Curvilinear motion

5.1.1 Introduction of Case study 1

A series preliminary experiments were taken out to test the possibility of using "HSK center rhythm monitor slim" to measure driver's comfortable feeling during driving. The first, whether the device would be interfered by the noise of driving condition; the second, if it was possible to evaluate driver's comfortableness quantitatively by using the device during the driving automobiles. The results showed "HSK center rhythm monitor slim" was hard to receive the influence of noise by the vibrations such as engine and glasses [11]; also, it was possible that this device could be used to evaluate driver's comfortableness during the movement of vehicle because the different expression of driver's comfortableness could be sufficiently observed in different driving courses [12].

The experiment was conducted driving the test car along a driving course with 180-degree cornering. Four subjects (Male with more than five years driving experience) were asked to do

the operations in the order shown as the table1. Every subject had to complete the course with SUMMER tire one time and STUDLESS tire one time.

Number Card	Operating procedure	Plan (or Top) view of the test course
1	Start engine, keep quiet for 25.6 seconds	
1-2	Accelerate to 20km/h	
2-3	Cornering by low speed	
3-4	Accelerate to 50-60km/h	
4-5	Cornering by high speed	
5-6	Decelerate to 20km/h	
1	Keep quiet until 204.8 seconds reached	

Table.1. Plan of 180-degree cornering course and driving procedure

Drivers' comfortableness was evaluated from two aspects of EEG and subjective evaluation in the experiment. In the aspect of EEG, the device "HSK center rhythm monitor slim" was used to record subjects' comfortableness in three indicators of valence, arousal and comfortableness degree in real time of course driving. In the aspect of subjective evaluation, after experiment, each subject was also asked to answer 2 questions to evaluate his comfortable feeling on the different speed of cornering and different tire. The first question was "which did you feel more comfort with high speed or low speed when cornering". The second question was "did you feel the difference about SUMMER tire or STUDLESS tire; which tire did you feel more comfort with when cornering".

In the other hand we got the vehicle's characteristics in movement by the original measurement device installed in the test car. We divided the characteristics in two parts of motion indicators and operation indicators.

5.1.2 Analysis and Results of Case Study 1 The Multiple Linear Regression and Simple Correlation were used to analyze the relationship between valence/arousal and vehicular characteristics in each cornering stage. Moreover Independent-samples T-Test was used to verify whether there was a difference of comfortableness degree between the differences of cornering speed or tire.

Analysis showed both the motion indicators and operation indicators had correlations with valence or arousal, the strong correlation between motion indicators and valence or arousal. No

difference of comfortableness degree was shown neither between the differences of cornering speed nor difference of tire; whereas the difference of comfort feeling on different cornering speed or tire were confirmed by drivers' subjective evaluation. All the subjects told that they feel more comfort in cornering with high speed than with low speed. 50-50% subjects separately felt more comfortable in two types of tire.

On the assumption that each driver was in the state which cognitive processing was mainly performed during driving, because the driver must be concentrated on driving to go through the course, it was clear that emotional reactions of comfortableness on driving information could be observed partly. But more emotional reactions on details of information, such as different information of tire or cornering speed, could not be observed through EEG. These concealed part of reactions through EEG, could be observed through subjective evaluation. In another words, we considered that even though some emotional reactions on information could not be observed through physiological responses of brain in the states that cognitive processing was mainly performed, they could be memorized subconsciously, and be recalled consciously through subjective evaluation.

5.2 Case study 2 Studying emotions excited by interface background color

5.2.1 Introduction of Case Study 2

Case study1 also showed that user's emotional physiological responses reacted on the information of vehicle motion; this indicated that emotion could be roused by physical information of interface. In case study 2, based on the results, we continued investigating whether the emotional reactions aroused by information of interface would effect on cognitive activities. We utilized the famous psychological experiment of "Mental-image Rotation"[13] to build the platform of research. According to this psychological experiment, when subjects were asked to judge whether two 3D mental images are same figures, there was a tendency that the judging time increased with the angle difference between two images increased.

We made a program realized the mental-rotation in virtual 3D space, in which user could rotate mental images to match with the designated image. The background colors of the program interface were designed in 4 types, gray, red, blue and favor colors that chose by user self. We expected, as the stimulant information effecting on user, different background color could rouse user's different emotional reactions; and through the comparison study among the 4 subject groups divided by background colors to investigate whether the emotional reactions effected on cognitive activities.

Figure2 Task process

Each group 5 persons, 4 groups totally 20 students of the University of Tsukuba took part into experiment. The experiment sequence is shown as figure 2 and figure 3. In each group, subject was required to operate the program by mouse to finish the 3 tasks; the task was ‘click the button on right side of interface to rotate the right image and match with left image’. The left image was fixed, and the initial angle of the right image was changed in each task. 3 tasks as one operating stage repeated 5 times. There was a short time rest break before each stage began. During the operation, subjects’ operating log data of mouse, such as operating time and clicks, were recorded as indicators of cognitive activities. In recording emotional reactions, we firstly used “HSK center rhythm monitor slim” to measure subjects’ comfort feeling when they operated the program. After the operation, Semantic Differential Method (SD Method) was used to record subjects’ emotional experiences on operation. In the questionnaire, ten pairs of adjective were listed, such as interesting-boring, amusing-laboring, favorable-detestable, smooth-jerky, energetic-tired, easy-difficult, sample-complex, calm-upset, relax-stress and satisfied-dissatisfied. There were 5 evaluating points in each pair of adjective.

Figure 3. Background Color Setting

5.2.2 Analysis and Results of Case Study 2

In order to investigate whether the background color effected on subjects, One-Way ANOVA was used to verify whether there were differences among the 4 groups in subjective evaluation (points of SD Method), comfortable feeling (valence, arousal and comfortableness degree) and operation (operating time and clicks). The results showed that there was tendency that subjects in the favorite color group had more “ positive and calming” comfortable state than other groups; subjects in the red color groups had more “negative and exciting” emotional state than other groups. But no differences in subjective evaluation or operation data were detected.

In order to view if there were common types of operation among the subjects, Hierarchical Cluster was used to classify the subjects’ operating time and clicks. The subjects were divided into 4 groups according to their common changing types that expressed in operating time of stage. There were also 4 clicks-changing types that expressed in operating clicks of stage. Between the 4-group types of operating time and subjective evaluation, Discriminate Analysis was used to investigate if there were relations between operation and subjective evaluation. The same analysis was used between the 4-clicks-changing types and subjective evaluation. The results showed that there was relation between clicks-changing types and subjective evaluation.

The group which operating clicks decreased with stages had tendency to evaluate more “easy” and “sample” than other group.

Correlation analysis showed that there was no correlation between operation (time or clicks) and comfortable feeling (valence or arousal or comfortableness degree).

Figure 4. The results of analysis of case study 2

Line-Regression analysis between comfortable feeling (valence or arousal or comfortableness degree) and subjective evaluation showed that there was no relation between them.

The results of analysis summarized in figure 4. Firstly, favorite color of background could induce user’s mood to more comfortable states. But no evident showed that these emotion reactions on color information were effected on operation. We consider that even though there were emotional physiological responses affected by interface information, these emotional reactions did not influence the cognitive activities in the states that cognitive processing was mainly performed. Next, there was relationship between the operation and emotional reactions recalled consciously by subjective evaluation. From this point, we consider that cognitive activities could effect on emotion, these influences were memorized subconsciously during the operation.

6. Discussions and Conclusion

In the research, we observed emotion from two aspects of physiological responses and subjective evaluation. The interactions between emotion and cognition showed different expressions from these two aspects.

In the aspects of physiological responses, emotion performed independently responding to dynamical information of interface while operation. It is possible that user preference information, such as color, would influence users mood. But no evidence showed that this influence expressed in physiological responses would change cognitive activities in the states

that cognition mainly performed during the operation. Furthermore, not all effects of emotion responding to dynamical information could be observed through psychological responses. We doubt that this is not only because of limitation of measurement on brain waves, but also the emotional evaluation on information was restrained by cognitive activities in the states that the cognition was mainly performed while user concentrated in operation.

In the aspects of subjective evaluation, even though there was some emotional experience that could not be measured by physiological responses, these contents could be recalled consciously by subjective evaluation. Sometimes, emotional evaluation showed relationships with operation. From the meaning, we considered that emotion could be elicited by cognition. Certainly, it is very difficult to record user subjective evaluations dynamically at the same time of operation. So what we could get is just confirmed the cognitional effects on emotion after operation. We believe that the emotional evaluation on former operations would possibly influent succeed operations, such as operating strategy making. This needs to be study by new research way in future research.

In this study, we proposed the Interaction Model between emotion and cognition in which the observing methods were also suggested. We believe the model will be useful for studying emotion and emotion evaluation in the research field of interface. The study indicates that emotion would be performed independently responding to information dynamically in the state that cognitive processing is mainly performed while using products. Sometimes emotional reactions show connections with cognition, even if it did not be reflected on operational behaviors and physiological indicators, it would be memorized implicitly, and aroused consciously by subjective evaluation after operation.

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